

TABLE CAPTIONS

TABLE 1. Published and unpublished data for long trackways made by single track-maker. Track-makers are all *Homo sapiens* except for N011 Laetoli (*Australopithecus aferensis*) and N012 Ileret (*Homo erectus*). Note that N013 fails the N=10 threshold but is included as the only published example of a trackway made in travertine. Values in square brackets for Shapiro-Wilk are not normal at 0.05 but are at 0.001.

TABLE 2. Published and unpublished experimental data made by a single track-maker. Values in square brackets for Shapiro-Wilk are not normal at 0.05 but are at 0.001.

TABLE 3. Basic summary data for the tridactyl (theropod) bipedal footprints at in Switzerland, Portugal, China and South Korea. Note that some of the primary distributions are not normally distributed.

TABLE 4. Basic summary data for the sauropod footprints from the Canton Jura tracksites (Switzerland). Note that some of the distributions are not normally distributed. PL stands for pes length and ML for manus length.

TABLE 5. Generic SE^{est} for different conditions with *Homo sapiens* track-makers. This based on the averages of 100 repetitions of the analysis. CIU: upper confidence interval at 0.05; CIL: lower confidence interval at 0.05

TABLE 6. Worked example of an MNI estimate using the scenario shown in Belvedere et al. (2021, Fig. 6). Errors are taken from the look-up table of generic errors in Table 5 based on all categories (fossil/experimental, soft/firm substrates) and in all but one case (comparison of tracks B and C) the difference between the means exceeds the maximum estimated SE^{est} at 95% CI. The tentative conclusion is that there is evidence for only three track-makers.